

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

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Title: SOP for replacing GC column of GC Exploris

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IMPORTANT:

- Fore Vacuum: 0.616 mbar
- HCD Cell Pressure: 1.1e-2 mbar
- UHV: 2e-10 mbar
- Aux Modules and Valves:
 - Heater 1: 280 (°C)
 - Heater 2: 280 (°C)
- Ion source temp. 280 (°C)

TO prepare GC Exploris for replacing the column

1. In Chromeleon 7 software > Thermo MS Tuning place instrument in the **OFF** state.
2. Cool the GC oven, Aux Heater 1 & Heater 2, Inlet, and Ion Source:
 - a. On the GC panel, press the „**Instrument control**“ and then „**Oven**“ to open submenu and set „**OFF**“ in temperature setpoint window see Figure 1.
 - b. On the GC panel, press the „**Maintenance**“ to open temperature menu change both **Aux Heater 1** and **Aux Heater 2** to „**YES**“ and press „**Begin Cooldown**“ see Figures 2.

Figure 1 Touch Screen Main Menu: Instrument Control

Figure 2 Touch Screen Main Menu: Maintenance

- c. In Chromeleon 7 > Thermo MS Tuning, set the ion source temperature around **20 °C**. When the temperature is $\sim 170^{\circ}\text{C}$ you can remove the ion source (higher temperature avoids excessive oxidation of source parts or contamination from the source plug).
- d. Turn the carrier gas flow of the Front inlet Off (Instrument Control > Front Inlet (PTV) > Column flow > Off).

NOTE: Wait until the system is cooled down otherwise the column will be destroyed.

- Using the source removal tool and vacuum interlock, remove the ion source.

Figure 3 Placing the ion Source Cartridge in the Source Holder

- Place the ion source cartridge on the source holder and put aside (on the desk covered with aluminum foil) see Figure 3.
- Place the source plug in the source plug holder see Figure 4 and then use the source exchange tool to attach the source plug placed in the source plug holder see Figure 5.

Figure 4 Source Plug in the Source Plug Holder

Figure 5 Attaching the Source Plug to the Source Exchange Tool

- Twist the Plug Exchange Tool until engraved grooves on the Plug Exchange Tool and on the Source Plug align securely see Figure 6.

NOTE: Be sure that the Source Plug is clean and without any dust particles on it. In that case, use compressed air to blow all particles off the source plug if needed before inserting.

Figure 6 Attached Source Plug to the Source Exchange Tool

7. Insert the barrel end of the source exchange tool into the vacuum interlock and twist it clockwise to lock it into the position. The black handle must be fully extended and locked see Figure 7.

Figure 7 Inserting the Source Plug into the Vacuum Interlock

Figure 8 Source Exchange Tool attached with Source Plug and connected to vacuum interlock

8. Once the source plug is inside the ion source chamber, leave the source plug attached to the source exchange tool and the source exchange tool connected to the vacuum interlock see Figure 8.

Siltite μ -Union connection of two capillary columns

NOTE: see video: <https://www.restek.com/en/video-library/connecting-GC-columns-using-a-siltite-micro-union/>

NOTE: Tools for connecting GC column with GC guard column:

Column: Rxi-5Sil MS; 0.25 μ m, 0.25 mmID; 15m length; Restek; cat. 13620 (use 15 m column)

Post-column: Rxi Guard Column 0.25 mmID; 5 m length; Restek; cat. 10029 (install only 2 m)

Pre-column: Rxi Guard Column; 0.53 mmID, 5 m length; Restek; cat. 10054 (install only 2 m)

Ferrule, SilTite; Replacements for MicroUnion; P/N 23896 (0.25-0.53 mm) RESTEK for GC guard column 0.53 ID

Ferrule, SilTite; Replacements for MicroUnion; P/N 23894 (0.25-0.25 mm) RESTEK

Connector, Siltite MicroUnion; P/N: 23885 RESTEK

Figure 9 Tools for connecting GC column with GC guard column

1. Slide the male μ -connector end fitting onto the capillary column. If you are connecting columns with different diameters, it is recommended to start with larger one first.
2. Insert the capillary column into the double taper ferrule and screw the male μ -connector end fitting into the position. Make sure the capillary column seats inside the ferrule all the time. Gently tighten male μ -connector end fitting with your fingers until you feel resistance see Figure 10.

- Slide a FingerTite μ -connector male/female end fitting tool over the capillary via the slot cut in the tool and place it on the male μ -connector end fitting. Tighten male μ -connector end fitting until the ferrule begins to hold onto the capillary column, then tighten a bit more (about 60°).

NOTE: Ferrule must hold onto the capillary column, but don't overtighten it.

Legend

- Ferrule/nut adaptor tool
- Connection nut
- SilTite double taper ferrule
- Capillary tubing (0.36 mm OD)
- Male μ -connector end fitting
- FingerTite μ -connector male/female end fitting tool

Figure 10 Exploded view of installing male μ -connector and fitting and double taper ferrule

Figure 11 Detail of male μ -connector and fitting and double taper ferrule

- Unscrew the ferrule/nut adaptor tool from the male μ -connector end fitting
- Slide the female μ -connector end fitting onto the capillary column.
- Insert the second capillary column into the double taper ferrule and screw the female μ -connector end fitting into the position. Make sure the capillary column seats inside the ferrule

all the time. Gently tighten female μ -connector end fitting with your fingers until you feel resistance see Figure 11.

Legend

- 3. SilTite double taper ferrule
- 4. Capillary tubing (0.36 mm OD)
- 5. Male μ -connector end fitting
- 6. FingerTite μ -connector male/female end fitting tool
- 7. Female μ -connector end fitting

Figure 12 Exploded view of Installing female μ -connector end fitting and double taper ferrule

Figure 13 Detail of female μ -connector end fitting and double taper ferrule

7. Slide a FingerTite μ -connector male/female end fitting tool over the capillary via the slot cut in the tool and place it on the female μ -connector end fitting. Tighten female μ -connector end fitting until the ferrule begins to hold onto the capillary column, then tighten a bit more (about 60 °) see Figure 14.

NOTE: Ferrule must hold onto the capillary column, but don't overtighten it

8. Remove both of the FingerTite μ -connector male/female end fitting tools from the male and female μ -connector end fitting and the capillary columns. Once again, check if both column ends hold in the double taper ferrule. If yes, you are ready to install the column into the instrument.

Capillary column installation guide

Column installation to MS

1. Open the GC oven door.
2. Unscrew the nut and remove the current column and nut.

NOTE: Do not forget to monitor the vacuum to confirm the source plug is properly sealing the transfer line.

NOTE: Cut off the old capillary and attach a septum to its end to provide a vacuum see Figure 14.

Figure 14 Column with attached septum

3. Unwind an appropriate column length to insert into the transfer line along the front of the instrument.
4. Carefully extend the column end out to allow application of the nut (**Collared Column Nut, Self-Tightening MSD, G3440-81013**) and ferrule (**Graphite /Vespel Ferrule 0.1-0.25mm, Pk 5, P/N 290VT221** (flat side of the ferrule faces the MS) see Figure 15.

Figure 15 Column with nut and ferrule (flat side on the ferrule faces the MS)

5. Use a scoring wafer to remove a bit of column to make a clean, perfect-cut end and wipe the column with methanol soaked - wipe after cutting.
6. Insert the column into the MS transfer line and tighten the nut until the column just resists sliding through the ferrule see Figure 16.

Figure 16 Inserting the Column into the MS transfer line

7. Loosen the nut $\frac{1}{4}$ turn and push the column into the MS transfer line carefully until the column touches the source plug.
8. Then pull the column about 1 mm away from the source plug and tighten the nut $\frac{1}{2}$ turn (depends on the fore vacuum value and leak but do not overtighten the nut) see Figure 16.

Column installation to the inlet

9. Unwind the inlet guard column (0.53mm ID) end to easily connect the end to the injector
10. Insert the column through the septum (holds the nut at the position), the nut, and proper ferrule (**M4 Fittings 1/16" X 0.8mm ID (Fits 0.53 mm ID column); 20285; RESTEK**); see Figure 17.
11. Use a scoring wafer to remove a bit of column to make a clean, perfect-cut end and wipe the column with methanol soaked-wipe after cutting (Use a magnifying glass to check the cut, repeat it if necessary. Demand for a perfect cut here is more important than of the MS column end)

Figure 17 Inserting the column into the injector

12. Position the column so that the end of the column extends the proper distance above the end of the ferrule (30 mm for PTV) see Figure 18.

Figure 18 Detail of nut and column with ferrule

13. Install the nut (do not overtighten it).

14. Insert the EI ion source back.
15. Restore Ion source temp. (°C) **280**.
16. In Chromeleon 7 software > Thermo MS Tuning put the instrument to **ON** mode.
17. **Set the carrier gas on, restore both Aux Heater 1 and Aux Heater 2 and Front (PTV) wait at least 1 hour** then restore the oven temperature (80°C).
18. After restoring **Aux Heater 1 and Aux Heater 2 and Front (PTV)** temperatures and stabilizing the system check for potential leaks in Chromeleon 7 software> Thermo MS Tuning > Optimization > Leak Check > Optimize (check also fore vacuum). If needed, tighten changed-nuts to gain proper sealing (ideally about 6% or less, acceptable is leak 10 %), but keep in mind to not overtighten it.
NOTE: Use low flow of argon for location of potential leak in the connections and monitor via signal in MS m/z = 39.948. Remember that during testing potential leak connection before column the time shift of signal of argon has to be expected.
NOTE: Tighten all the connections, the next day the connections need to be retighten due to thermal expansion of the ferrule material; especially after column conditioning.
19. Condition the new column following manual for each column length and brand (typically 10 hours).
NOTE: Start conditioning the column when the leak is around 10 % or less, otherwise there is a risk of column damage.
20. Insert the method for conditioning the column and submit the sequence.
21. After conditioning the column change source if needed.
NOTE: During column conditioning, siloxanes are released which typically contaminate the source. Theoretically, it is possible to remove the column from the source for conditioning the column, unfortunately, the Chromeleon 7 software does not allow this procedure.

Conditioning method

TriPlus RSH

Step 1- Wait For Sync Signal (GC)	GC	GC1
Step 1- Wait For Sync Signal (GC)	GC	GC1
	Signal	Injected

GC Inlets (Trace1300/1310)

Front Inlet Options	Use this inlet ✓	
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	Enable temperature control ✓		
	Temperature	290°C	
Inlet Parameters	Operation mode	Splitless	
	Split flow control		
	Splitless time	1 min	
	Purge flow control ✓		
	Purge flow	5 ml/min	
	Constant setup purge ✓		
	Vacuum compensation		
	Enable gas saver mode ✓	Gas Saver Flow 20.0 ml/min	
		Gas saver time 5.00 min	
PTV Ramp Settings	Injection	Time 0.05 min	
	Transfer	Rate 14.5°C/s	
		Temp 200°C	
		Time 1.00 min	
	Cleaning		
Enable evaporation phase	/		
Enable clean phase	/		
Enable pressure ramps	/		
Post cycle temperature	Off		
FrontInlet Flow/Pressure Options	Constant flow	1.2 ml/min	

GC Oven Settings (Trace 1300/1310)

Prep Run Timeout	10 min		
Oven equilibration time	1.0 min		
Ready delay	0.0 min		
Mode	Ramped temperature		
Retention time [min]	Rate [°C/min]	Target value [°C]	Hold time [min]
0.000	Run		
5.000	0.00	40	5.0
330	2.00	330	180
369	10	40	10
607	5	330	180
607	StopRun		

GC Aux Heaters (TRACE1300/1310)

Heater1	Enable ✓	
	Temperature	280°C
Heater2	Enable ✓	

	Temperature	280°C
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GC (TRACE1300/1310)

Column: Rxi-5Sil MS; 0.25 um, 0.25 mmID; 15m length; Restek; cat. 13620 (use 15 m column)

Post-column: Rxi Guard Column 0.25 mmID; 5 m length; Restek; cat. 10029 (install only 2 m)

Pre-column: Rxi Guard Column; 0.53 mmID, 5 m length; Restek; cat. 10054 (install only 2 m)

Collared Column Nut, Self Tightening MSD; Agilent Technologies; cat. G3440-8113

To MS: Ferules VG1 0.4 mm; 85% Vespel/15% Graphite (Fits column ID ≤ 0.25 mm); Restek; cat. 27071

To inlet: Nut M4 with carving; Thermo Scientific;cat. 35003221

To inlet: M4 Fittings 1/16" x 0.8 mm ID (Fits 0.53 mm ID column; Restek; cat. 20285

Liner: Split Liner, 2 mm x 2.75 x 120 for Thermo GCs; Siltek Deact.; w/Deact. Wool, 5pk; cat. 21117-213

O-ring: O-ring parofluor 2-005; Thermo Scientific; cat. 29001318

FrontColumn	Validate column configuration✓	
	Length	15.00 m
	Diameter	0.25 mm
	Film thickness	0.25 µm

MSDevice (Orbitrap Exploris GC 240)

Global Parameters

Application Mode	Default		
Method Duration (min)	607		
Internal Mass Calibration	Off		
Ion Source Properties	Filament Power Table	Time (min)	State
	1	0	Off
	2	2	Off
	Use Ion Source Settings from Tune	/	
	Ion Source Temp	280	
	Ionization Mode	EI	
	Calibration Gas	Use From Tune	
	Filament	Static	
	Emission Current	50	
	Electron Energy	70	
	Electron Lens	15	
	C -Trap Offset	Use From Tune	

	Optics	Use From Tune	
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Scan Parameters

Full Scan	Full Scan Properties	Orbitrap Resolution	60 000
		Scan Range (m/z)	70-700
		AGC Target	Custom
		Normalized AGC Target (%)	100
		Maximum Injection Time Mode	Auto
		Microscans	1
		Data Type	Profile
		Polarity	Positive

System

Run Time	607.000 min
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